

Impact of the General Data Protection Law (LGPD) on Agile Software Development.

This questionnaire aims to identify how software development teams that use agile methodologies are carrying out the privacy requirements elicitation after the LGPD comes into force. If you don't work with agile methodologies and don't know the LGPD, we appreciate your interest in participating. The questions addressed in this questionnaire are for developers and/or project managers who work with agile methodologies and LGPD.

STATEMENT OF INFORMED CONSENT

By answering this survey, you allow the researchers to obtain, use and disclose the anonymous information provided as described below.

CONDITIONS AND STIPULATIONS

1. I understand that all information is confidential. I will not be personally identified. I agree to complete the survey for research purposes and that the data derived from this anonymous survey may be published in journals, conferences and blog posts.
2. I understand that my participation in this research survey is totally voluntary, and that declining to participate will involve no penalty or loss of benefits. If I choose, I may withdraw my participation at any time. I also understand that if I choose to participate, that I may decline to answer any question that I am not comfortable answering.
3. I understand that I can contact the researchers if I have any questions about the research survey. I am aware that my consent will not directly benefit me. I am also aware that the author will maintain the data collected in perpetuity and may utilize data for future academic work.
4. By clicking the button below, I freely provide consent and acknowledge my rights as a voluntary research participant as outlined above and provide consent to the researchers to use my information in conducting research on the areas noted above.

*THIS FORM TAKES ABOUT 10 MINUTES TO COMPLETE.

* Required

1. P1. Please let us know what is your Country, State and City where you are working in the industry. *

2. P2. How old are you? *

Mark only one oval.

- under 21 years old
- 21 to 25 years
- 26 to 30 years
- 31 to 36 years
- 37 to 42 years
- 43 to 47 years
- 48 to 54 anos
- 55 to 60 years
- more than 61 years

3. P3. What is your degree of education? *

Mark only one oval.

- Undergraduate Student
- Graduated
- Master
- Especialization
- PhD

4. P4. How long have you been working in ICT? *

Mark only one oval.

- less than 1 year
- 1 to 3 years
- 4 to 6 years
- 7 to 10 years
- 11 to 15 years
- 16 to 20 years
- more than 21 years

5. P5. In which area of your organization did you participate/participate in a software development project? *

Mark only one oval.

- Federal Public Administration
- State Public Administration
- Private software development companies
- State-owned company
- Research/collaboration projects
- Open source software projects

6. P6. Do you work or have you worked with agile development teams? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

7. P7. What was the main role (roles) you perform/performed in a software development project? *

Check all that apply.

- Requirements Analyst
- Data Modeling
- Software Engineer
- Programmer/Developer
- Software Tester
- Designer
- Project Manager
- Human-Computer Interaction specialist

8. P8. Do you work or have you worked on developing software functionality that had data privacy concerns? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

9. P9. My organization has implemented or is implementing changes due to the LGPD? *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

10. P10. My knowledge about the Brazilian General Data Protection Law (LGPD), which was implemented in 2020, is sufficient for the development of my activities in the projects I am participating in. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

11. P11. Which of the principles of the Brazilian General Data Protection Law (LGPD) do you know? *

Check all that apply.

1. Purpose: execution of the processing for legitimate, specific, explicit and informed purposes to the data subject, with no possibility of further processing in a manner incompatible with those purposes.

2. Adequacy: Agreement of processing with the purposes reported to the data holder, being consistent with the context of the processing.

3. Needs: Limitation of the treatment to the minimum necessary to achieve its ends, with coverage of relevant data, proportional and not excessive concerning the data processing purposes;

4. Open Access: Assurance to data subjects, free and accessible information about the form and duration of data processing, as well as the completeness of their sensitive data.

5. Data Quality: Ensure data holders the accuracy, clarity, relevance, and updating of the data, as necessary, and the purposes of its processing.

6. Transparency: Guarantee, to the data holders, of precise, reliable and readily available information on the execution of the processing and its corresponding processing agents, subject to commercial and industrial secrets.

7. Security: Use of administrative and technical standards to protect personal data from unauthorized access and unexpected or unlawful situations of destruction, loss, alteration, communication, or dissemination.

8. Prevention: Adoption of means to prevent the appearance of damages due to the personal data processing.

9. Non-discrimination: Inability to perform data processing for illicit or abusive discriminatory purposes. The data subject has the right to request a review of the decision, and the supervisory authority may examine it to check discriminatory aspects in the automated processing of personal data.

10. Accountability and Legal reporting: The agent demonstrates the adoption of effective measures, capable of proving the observance and compliance with personal data protection rules, including the effectiveness of such measures.

12. P12. Which of the LGPD principles does your organization use/implement? *

Check all that apply.

1. Purpose

2. Adequacy

3. Needs

4. Open Access

5. Data Quality

6. Transparency

7. Security

8. Prevention

9. Non-discrimination

10. Accountability and Legal reporting

13. P13. Which data privacy solutions have you worked or currently work with? *

Check all that apply.

- Encryption
- User's control
- User's Access
- Automatic Expiration Data
- Data Anonymization
- Decentralization
- User's Deletion
- Temporal Data

14. P14. In your perception, the changes proposed by LGPD impact which knowledge area in the software development process? *

Check all that apply.

- Software Requirements
- Software Design
- Software Construction
- Software Testing
- Software Maintenance
- Software Configuration Management
- Software Engineering Management
- Software Engineering Process
- Software Engineering Models and Methods
- Software Quality

15. P15. Select the tools used by your software development team to elicit and document privacy requirements. *

Check all that apply.

- Pris
- Sectro
- PCM
- Pret
- STS
- DPIA
- IDEMIX
- OASIS PMRM
- SMaRT
- Strap
- RMCM-V
- SPARQL
- None
- Other: _____

16. P16. Do you think the organizational environment interferes with data privacy practices? *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

17. P17. The organization I work for has informed all of its employees about the Brazilian General Data Protection Law (LGPD) and its implementation in 2020. In addition, discussions were held with the teams regarding possible changes that would be required to current and future systems. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

18. P18. After the LGPD came into effect, the way my organization's teams work has changed. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

19. P19. Organizational procedures related to user data privacy should be known to all employees in the organization, including the software development team. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

20. P20. Do you think that the criteria used to determine which work items are critical with respect to data privacy should be based on data protection objectives? *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

21. P21. Defining a set of privacy requirements before the requirements elicitation stage can compromise the agility of the software development process. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

22. P22. The data protection set initially defined by the development team must be evolved/changed throughout the software development process. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

23. P23. Using documents from traditional methodologies, e.g. data flow diagram, architecture overview, data model, class diagram, etc., to identify the flow of data privacy-related information can facilitate the identification and documentation of privacy requirements. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

24. P24. The data model or class diagram can be used to identify and document the privacy requirements of a piece of software. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

25. P25. Specifying the privacy requirements of the system can be done using use cases or user stories. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutro
- Agree
- Strongly agree

26. P26. If your software development team performs the specification of privacy requirements using user stories, at what point and how are data privacy related aspects (purpose, adequacy, consent, documentation, accountability, among others) inserted? *

Check all that apply.

- Business Modeling
- Requirements
- Analysis and design
- Development
- Test
- Deployment and Maintenance

27. P27. If your development team (and you) uses user stories, what difficulties do you identify, regarding the implementation of data privacy principles (purpose, adequacy, consent, security, prevention, documentation, accountability and others) in the agile software development process? *

28. P28. Do you think that outdated user stories can be a threat to the correct implementation of privacy requirements? Please justify your answer. *

29. P29. Do you think that specifying privacy requirements using user stories or use cases in the requirements specification phase (early design phase) is sufficient for correctly ensuring the privacy of users' data? *

30. P30. What other practices do you think can be used by agile teams to implement LGPD principles? Could you please describe them? *

31. P31. Does your organization use any software to ensure compliance with LGPD? If so could you please describe the name of the software and its purpose? *

32. P32. After the LGPD came into effect and the penalties were charged for non-compliance starting in August 2021, could you describe to us whether your organization has modified the software development process to address privacy requirements? If so, could you describe to us what modifications were made to address privacy requirements during software development? *

33. P33. Does your organization use an LGPD compliance guide? Or have you created a guide? If so, could you please describe which one and if available what is the link to access it? *

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Contact
for
interview

If you can give us an interview to talk a little more about the practices adopted to elicit privacy requirements, please fill in the details below. We thank you very much in advance for your cooperation.

34. P34. Are you interested in participating in an interview about data privacy and LGPD in agile projects? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

35. P35. What is your contact? (Phone or e-mail) *

36. P.36 What is the best time to contact you? *

Check all that apply.

In the morning

In the afternoon

In the evening

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